

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Partnership for Remote Inventory,
Status & Management (PRISM) – A Case Study

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**Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study**

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Contents

Introduction 3

Partnership for Remote Inventory, Status and Management (PRISM) 4

 Results - Bottom Line Up Front (BLUF)..... 10

 Project Guidelines, Goals and Objectives 13

 Accomplishments, Key Findings & Foundational Support 15

 Subsequent PRISM Developments..... 18

Drone Lidar Scanning (DLS) and Imagery Data Collection 23

 GatorEye..... 23

 Data Collection..... 25

 The PRISM Difference..... 28

Operational Support 36

 ORC-CS 36

 ORCA-CS 36

 Field Equipment 37

Costs..... 38

Partners 39

Summary and Conclusions..... 40

 Legislative Subjunction..... 40

 Other Agency PRISM-Type Use Cases 41

 What’s Next?..... 45

Appendix A..... 47

References..... 64

Points of Contact..... 66

Acknowledgements..... 67

Introduction

On September 22, 2021, the [USDA Forest Service \(USFS\)](#) and the [University of Florida \(UF\)](#) formally established the 3-year Partnership for Remote Inventory, Status & Management (a.k.a. PRISM Project) by leveraging funds from the Additional Supplemental Appropriations for Disaster Relief Act, 2019 ([H.R.2157](#)) to launch PRISM and help determine the utility, applicability and associated costs for a large-area drone-borne spatial data collection effort over approximately half (~350,000 acres including flight revisits and value-added products) of the [Apalachicola National Forest \(ANF\)](#) (Figures 1 & 14). The ANF is situated in and greatly contributes to the biological diversity of one of the top North American “biodiversity hotspots” (Blaustein, 2008; Stein, Kutner & Adams, 2000) and represents a “significant landscape” for longleaf pine conservation and restoration (America’s Longleaf, 2009). PRISM was established through a challenge cost share agreement for \$1,398,985.04 awarded to [UF’s Spatial Ecology & Conservation \(SPEC\) Lab](#) who have worked directly with the [Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration \(CSER\)](#) at [Florida A&M University \(FAMU\)](#) to successfully collect, analyze and deliver dense drone-borne lidar data and imagery over the western half of the ANF (Apalachicola Ranger District) that was impacted by Hurricane Michael on October 10, 2018.

Figure 1. High quality longleaf pine habitat with healthy wiregrass groundcover vegetation located in the western portion of the Apalachicola National Forest near Sumatra, Florida. This image represents stable, mature longleaf habitat considered by many to be a representative “top-tier” reference condition example of open-canopy longleaf pine habitat across the southeastern U.S. (Image: J. Drake, USFS, 2016).

Hurricane Michael was a catastrophic category 5 storm that affected at least 28% of the remaining global longleaf pine extent (Zampieri, Pau & Okamoto, 2020) and resulted in extensive tree mortality (Figure 2) across 18 counties that damaged an estimated \$1.3 billion worth of timber on approximately 2.8 million acres of land (Florida Forest Service, 2018). Despite its tragic and costly nature, this event highlighted the importance of developing timely, post-disaster landscape-scale timber damage assessments. It also unlocked opportunities for multi-party cooperation and represents a functional government-academic-industry alliance utilizing the very latest commercial U.S. technological advances

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

in remote sensing to help evaluate timber and natural resource damage, aid in the restoration of affected areas, and pave the way for increased agency readiness for storms and other natural disasters. In addition to the primary goal of timber/natural resource damage assessments, the PRISM Project underscores the necessity to deploy advanced U.S.-made National Defense Authorization Act (NDAA) compliant remote sensing technologies for efficient, data-directed decision-making applied to a wide variety of landscape-scale agency management initiatives including prescribed fire, wildfire, silviculture, geospatial ecology and hydrology among others.

Figure 2. Catastrophic timber stand damage near the Apalachicola National Forest Chipola Tract following Hurricane Michael that made landfall on October 10, 2018 (Image, M. Keys, 2018)

Partnership for Remote Inventory, Status and Management (PRISM)

PRISM is a [USFS \(Region 08\)](#)-funded, [Natural Resource Conservation Service \(NRCS\)](#), [RESTORE](#)-supported initiative. While primarily focused on post-Hurricane Michael timber stand damage, PRISM helps move the needle for remote landscape-scale land management, related decision-support, and serves as an effective model for accelerating adoption of the very latest remote sensing and artificial intelligence technologies applied to large landscape analytics for creating detailed characterizations and useful metrics used to manage vast natural and modified landscapes. As mentioned, PRISM takes full advantage of the most recent U.S.-made technological advances including improvements in remote aerial data collection platforms, unconventional but complimentary sensor arrays, highly accurate onboard geo-positioning systems, novel component materials and miniaturization, high-performance

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

and spatial computing, mobile command/control field operations support, multi-temporal, thermal and hyperspectral spatial analytics, and applied synchronous artificial intelligence that can all be directed towards the main objectives and provisions of [long-standing federal legislation](#) allowing the USFS and other federal land management agencies to deliver more comprehensive, and timely services to the public while reducing costs, improving safety and efficiency, and most importantly delivering previously unforeseen data and analytical capabilities to support efficient planning, decision-making and broad-area terrestrial and hydrologic restoration efforts for the benefit of the American public and the United States.

An advantage of PRISM is that it was built upon and still benefits from an established relationship between UF's SPEC Lab and CSER at FAMU, also a formal partnership between the USFS and FAMU since 2018. For years, staff at the U.S. Forest Service, National Forests in Florida (NFF) and CSER have worked closely with faculty, staff and students at UF's SPEC Lab prior to, during and after the PRISM Project launch and throughout our previously funded [Tate's Hell Strategy 1 \(THS1\) Project](#). Through the CSER-SPEC partnership, the PRISM Project, and other [RESTORE](#)-funded initiatives, our team with decades of experience have had the opportunity to collaborate and develop data collection and processing algorithms for novel analytical workflows related to the capture and production of drone-borne lidar, imagery and vector data including next-generation hypercubic fusion datasets applicable within the context of landscape ecology, forestry, hydrology, natural disasters (floods, fires, disease), and conservation and restoration activities across very large landscapes.

In recent years, CSER, SPEC and our partners have developed several analytical projects to assess timber stand damage related to windstorms and other natural catastrophes. St. Peter, et al., 2020¹ describes an early scenario where we used Sentinel-2 imagery, and 248 RESTORE-funded forest vegetation plots collected in the Apalachicola Region just prior to Hurricane Michael's landfall in 2018 to help quantify damage to forests. This study used a general linear model to predict tree basal area loss from Hurricane Michael across millions of acres of Florida landscape. The model was constrained to areas where trees were present using a tree presence model as a hurdle. We informed the model with post-hurricane Sentinel-2 imagery and compared the pre- and post-hurricane basal area maps to assess the total loss and damage to trees following the hurricane. After the event, field vegetation plots were revisited to ground-truth the modeled results which showed that the model performed well at categorizing forest hurricane damage (Figure 3). While our results validated this novel method to create landscape scale spatial datasets showing the location and intensity of basal area loss at 10-m spatial resolution to quantify forest disturbances, we felt that this phase was simply the first iterative step in an evolving geospatial analytical process applied to timber stand damage from windstorms and other disasters. The basal area model had an r-squared value of 0.508, and proved promising, but required a more robust lidar-based approach which was later adopted. This technique was also tested and validated on other Gulf Coast hurricanes including Laura that struck Louisiana at Cameron and the Kisatchie National Forest on August 27, 2020 (Figure 4).

As well, similar projects have arisen and remain in motion including the SPEC-CSER collaboration with the USFS [Forest Inventory and Analysis \(FIA\) Program](#) to advance post-storm disaster assessments in a USFS FIA-funded project called "[Storm Cloud](#)." This project leverages several advanced methods developed and described by UF's SPEC Lab researchers, FAMU's CSER and USFS personnel including a prototype application that has been produced to analyze remote, post-disaster forest vegetation damage data in near real-time. Specifically, the Storm Cloud system integrates satellite radar data that can

¹ CSER's research related to storm damage assessments evolved from prior collaborations with Drs. John Hogland and Nate Anderson at the USFS Rocky Mountain Research Station, Missoula, MT and has its roots firmly planted in a National Fish & Wildlife Foundation (NFWF)-funded Longleaf Alliance initiative called "The Longleaf Mapping Project."

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

penetrate cloud cover, to offer more complete and timely coverage following storm events. To accomplish this, Storm Cloud uses Sentinel-1 synthetic aperture radar (SAR), Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery, and combinations of both remote sensing datasets and FIA field data. Thus far, the results have far exceeded our expectations in terms of accuracy/predictability and could serve as a springboard for agency initiatives to evaluate catastrophic loss of timber resources. A beta release of the [Storm Cloud Disturbance Assessment Module](#) is openly available for interactive viewing on the [Google Earth Engine](#) planetary-scale geospatial platform for Earth science data and analysis (Figure 5). The Storm Cloud Application represents a live dynamic system which uses the most updated remote sensing data to provide near-real-time results. Additionally, Dr. Gabriel Prata, a Postdoctoral Researcher funded by RESTORE/CSER who worked on the Storm Cloud Project at the UF SPEC Laboratory, has made significant contributions to the remotely sensed storm damage effort (Prata et al., 2020). Dr. Prata's work with drone-borne lidar technology has been exceptional, demonstrating the ability to identify damaged and fallen trees in UAS-derived lidar point clouds, even with rapid, single-pass scanning techniques designed for speedy field deployments and near-real-time remote forest damage assessments (Figure 6).

Lastly, at a very early developmental stage of this process, two Microsoft AI for Earth grants were awarded to CSER that resulted in an extended working relationship with Microsoft program managers, engineers and analysts utilizing Azure Cloud Services to process lidar data associated with storm-related damage and also included unified radar data that can penetrate cloud cover, to offer more complete and timely coverage following storm events. Throughout our collaboration with Microsoft, the exploratory methods, products and cloud computing experience helped build the knowledge base for CSER, PRISM, and our most recent RESTORE-funded project – [The Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative \(ARRI\) Strategies 2&3](#) that includes a significant drone-borne lidar-based monitoring and adaptive management (MAM) element while using more advanced technology than was previously used for PRISM. All the above-mentioned endeavors provide valuable perspective about the time and effort that went into PRISM before, during and after project completion. As a result, the return on investment for PRISM is exceedingly high, and touts a partnership structure that has afforded fiscal efficiency, sustained advancement and partner leverage over time. All these elements have coalesced to provide intrinsic value and expanded capabilities to the agency, PRISM, ARRI and future projects.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure 3. Results from CSER's study to assess large-area storm timber damage within the Apalachicola and Big Bend Regions of Florida. The top image shows CSER's image-based (Sentinel 2) approach across the region while the image below depicts a zoomed-in detailed illustration of the analysis results that later evolved into lidar-based analysis techniques (St. Peter et al., 2020), before adopting Storm Cloud.

Figure 4. Hurricane Laura (8/27/2020) timber damage estimates (light to severe) for the Kisatchie National Forest using image-based analytical protocols described in St. Peter, et al., 2020.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

Figure 5. The beta Storm Cloud Google Earth Engine application exhibits accurate advanced processes with key analytical refinements for post-storm timber damage assessments developed by UF's SPEC Lab in partnership with USFS FIA, CSER and RESTORE. The red marker shows the location of Sumatra, Florida. Appropriate masks for water and forest are applied and show only areas with trees present. Image clarity enhanced on upper image frame.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

Figure 6. Single-pass drone flight test sites across hurricane-damaged areas of the Apalachicola National Forest. Red damage site polygons indicate eight UAV-LiDAR survey locations. Numbered boxes (1 to 8) represent locations with canopy height models (CHM). Dashed strips denote single-pass flightlines, and green boxes mark the 43 plots (130 m × 430 m each) used for ground-truthing (Prata et al., 2020).

Results - Bottom Line Up Front (BLUF)

The following excerpt from the USFS Geospatial Technology & Applications Center (GTAC) document, titled “Lidar Acquisitions Specifications for Forestry” from the USFS National Lidar Strategy playbook, effectively articulates our ongoing stance regarding drone-borne lidar acquisitions within the agency for natural resource-related data applications:

"In order to effectively support many natural resource management decisions, the USDA Forest Service (USFS) requires information about the vertical and horizontal structure of vegetation and the underlying terrain. Light Detection and Ranging (lidar) provides unique three-dimensional (3D) information that simultaneously measures the ground surface and forest canopy structure across acquisition areas in a comprehensive and accurate way that no other remote sensing technology currently offers." -GTAC, 2018

While we concur completely with the above statement, we would go further and say that this is now more pertinent than ever and should be one of the highest priorities for all land management agencies. The technology related workflows paired with rich astonishing datasets that stem from PRISM and other analytical lidar initiatives within the federal government have the potential to help reimagine

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

and replace costly, time-consuming, decades-old manual field-based vegetation assessment workflows, or at the very least highly amplify their efficacy. At this point, and in the spirit of transparency and BLUF, we make note of [Appendix A](#) below, where we provide numerous representative examples of the analytical potential modern high-density lidar data conjoined with spatial ecology, hydrology, and ecosystem restoration have to offer all land management agencies applicable to a wide variety of missions. Frankly, the possibilities are endless and collaborative government-academic-industry partnerships like PRISM would position federal land management organizations competitively when juxtaposed with outsourcing these tasks, especially when many contracting organizations do not wholly understand all the timber/natural resource issues specific to individual forests or regions. This information technology in the hands of local practitioners, in turn, provides enhanced federal force multiplication to help tackle some of the greatest natural resource problems we face as land managers and on an unprecedented scale.

To illustrate the potential of PRISM-style data, CSER compared agency post-storm Field Sampled Vegetation (FSVeg) data with PRISM lidar-derived results. USFS FSVeg (tabular and spatial) are internal systems and data resources used to maintain information associated with U.S. national forest stand vegetation characteristics. The system includes a database, and national protocols for collecting Common Stand Exam (CSE) information, and provides an interface with data entry, edit, management, and analysis capabilities. The data is designed to store field sampled vegetation data, including stand exams, permanent plot inventories, growth and yield plots, and forest health surveys. Fortunately, recent CSE plots were available to the PRISM Team having been recently collected using the same disaster relief funds that supported the PRISM Project. Some comparative examples between CSE and lidar-derived results are shown in the appendix. These comparisons demonstrate the accuracy and potential of both lidar-derived and field-derived metrics, and how they can be used synergistically with other applicable agency information to develop highly accurate, cost-effective, reliable stand vegetation data more rapidly.

Additionally, CSER and partners are exploring improved methods to ensure that verifiable field vegetation data and remotely sensed information can jointly support a more robust predictive modeling approach (ML, AI) for pre- and post-storm digital mensuration and change detection. This logic is also partially explained through the [“Big Plot Network”](#) operating model. The Big Plot Network (BPN), co-directed by Eben North Broadbent, and Angelica Maria Almeyda Zambrano arose from UF’s SPEC Lab and spans South, Central, and North America. It has also been implemented over portions of the Apalachicola Region including the ANF. The network now consists of >100 “big plots” (500 x 500 meters to 1500 x 1500 meters). Also, in the Southeast, the Big Plot Network focal areas include blue carbon regions (e.g., mangroves) and terrestrial forests affected by disturbances (e.g., fires, hurricanes, floods, etc.). As is the case with PRISM, data from Big Plots include ultra-high-density LiDAR point clouds, high-resolution 3D hyperspectral reflectance data, calibrated radiometric thermal point clouds, and high-resolution visual imagery, all gathered using the GatorEye Unmanned Flying Laboratory with standardized protocols and geo-synchronized point clouds and imagery datasets that can be fused for next-level analytics. Yet again, all of this has been leveraged for PRISM.

Given the current trajectory of drone-borne data acquisitions, it is very likely that the trend of highly accurate and economical DLS collection systems and methods, accompanied by advanced analytical processing procedures and existing data, will continue. We believe that much of this activity will eventually progress to semi-autonomous or even fully autonomous processes which are well beyond the scope of this initiative, but increasingly imminent. Furthermore, the treasured landscape within the Apalachicola Region is under threat. Extreme weather events, post-hurricane wildfire risks and resulting excess fuels from dead trees and downed woody debris have created significant headwinds for the remaining longleaf pine habitat within the Region. The Big Bend area of Florida has repeatedly been struck by major hurricanes and tropical storms (Figures 7 & 8). Whether from multiple large storms,

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

wildfires, or other natural disasters, PRISM sets the pace for deriving advanced remotely sensed geospatial solutions and derivatives to help create digital data baselines that help us trend towards **timber/natural resource resiliency** in the face of unpredictable natural disasters all while navigating through the ever-evolving progression towards societal transformation and comprehensive large landscape digitalization.

Figure 7. Major storms that made landfall in the Florida Panhandle within the last decade, including the incredibly destructive Category 5 Hurricane Michael that landed at Mexico Beach on October 10, 2018. Colored storm tracks indicate storm category wind strength are labeled for individual storms. See map legend for more details.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

Figure 8. Track of Category 4 Hurricane Helene that made landfall near Perry, FL on September 26, 2024, shown over major biodiversity hotspots in the southeastern U.S. Hurricane Helene was very destructive to many residents across several southeastern states and impacted numerous highly biodiverse habitats.

Project Guidelines, Goals and Objectives

Per USFS, Region 08 administrative guidelines, the following items were outlined as key elements to track, characterize and/or address over the duration of the PRISM Project:

- Purpose
 - Collect next-generation drone-borne lidar and imagery for the Apalachicola Ranger District on the western half of the Apalachicola National Forest.
 - Document the cooperation between participating parties to collect, process and analyze lidar and imagery data to aid in post-disaster recovery as well as restoration and monitoring in accordance with the provisions of the agreement, Statement of Work, Financial Plan, and Budget Narrative.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

- Objectives
 - Collect, analyze, manage and deliver all data and derivatives to the USFS in Q1 2025 as per the agreement.
 - Monitor general status of agreement execution.
 - Characterize risks and how they have played out (or not) and take corrective actions to address risks.
 - Identify early successes.
 - Provide germane data examples and use cases to the USFS R08 RIM unit showing the value, utility and potential to use high-density drone-borne lidar to characterize forested landscapes at multiple scales and relate them to post-hurricane disaster assessment, monitoring, and recovery activities relative to the agency mission.
 - Document costs, successes, and failures to help determine agency utility and implementation potential.
- Scope
 - Data Collection.
 - Information Management (including data management, storage, and processing).
 - Data and derivative delivery by Q1 2025.
 - Grants and Agreements (expenditures, monitoring, accomplishments tracking).
 - Ensure safety, security, efficiency.
- Future Emphasis Areas
 - Present applications and data specifically related to windstorm damage, decision support as well as education and recruiting potential.
- Outcomes (Minimum)
 - High-quality, accurate lidar data point clouds and high-resolution imagery for the Apalachicola Ranger District.
 - Note: Ultra-resolution, highly accurate RGB imagery is included as a PRISM deliverable and is directly encoded within the lidar data. Lidar and corresponding (encoded) imagery span the entire Apalachicola Ranger District.
 - Additionally, a thorough alignment procedure was conducted by UF to ensure that PRISM lidar aligns tightly with both 2018 and 2020 airborne lidar data. This was not part of the required deliverables but provides the agency and PRISM Team with a multi-year, error-corrected, highly co-aligned data archive baseline for assessing multi-temporal forest vegetation changes. The value of this cannot be understated.
 - See description of ALS and DLS co-alignment procedures later in this document.
 - Quarterly progress reports, and a final report documenting findings with recommendations across the scoped project including incidental topics and observations for consideration by the Regional Forester, National Forests in Florida Supervisor and interested stakeholders.

Accomplishments, Key Findings & Foundational Support

- Dense (150 pls/m² plus) drone-borne data successfully collected over approximately 350,000 acres that includes value-added products and flight revisits for critical areas that are being actively used to characterize treasured forested landscapes, and vital water resources for some of the most important fisheries and biodiverse lands in the world.
 - This achievement is an undocumented world record, agreed upon by leading industry and academic collaborators, and handily sets the bar at a high level moving forward. In fact, this monumental effort required over 500 flight hours spanning a three-year period, under extreme conditions from 20°F to 120°F, high winds, hurricanes, fog, and rainfall. This feat represents a 10x+ increase over any similar known effort. These missions were conducted using the Harris Aerial H6 EFI drone platform, which demonstrated remarkable endurance by flying over 14,000 km—equivalent to a flight from Tallahassee to the South Pole or over 40% of Earth’s equatorial circumference (Figure 9).
- Provided nearly 15 TB of the best data and derivatives (of this type) in the world to the USFS Geospatial Technology Applications Center (GTAC) for further exploration and development.
 - Existing data and derivatives produced from PRISM have been quality verified and show tremendous potential for further growth and exploration that could eventually provide a dense data foundation of well over one-half of a petabyte (PB) of relevant information if the appropriate resources are allocated to this and similar initiatives.
- As a mechanism to transfer technology directly to land management practitioners, CSER and PRISM have prepared and delivered data and derivatives to administrative and district personnel for use across USFS National Forests in Florida lands to help manage and plan forest activities. In fact, the users continue to request these types of products from us.
 - The National Forests in Florida and Apalachicola National Forest district staff have already used region-wide CSER data and derivatives for years and will undoubtedly use PRISM data to help guide future management decisions (e.g., ~5,658,713 acres of basal area coverage in fine scale raster data format used for assessing tree density to provide insights into timber volume and the overall health and productivity of forested stands).
- Provided exceptional coordination with the USFS R8 Fire and Aviation Management (FAM) unit and the Florida Interagency Coordination Center (FICC), including safe operational workflows used for flight deconfliction and field activities. This paves the way for future, PRISM-type activities for timber and natural resource damage assessment as well as assessment and monitoring for timber operational activities.
- Prior to PRISM, 248 “RESTORE Plots²” funded by Restore the Gulf were developed by CSER in partnership with the USFS Rocky Mountain Research Station, and Florida State University’s Florida Natural Area Inventory. Fortunately, these plots were sampled just prior to Hurricane Michael’s landfall and were imperative to the launch of PRISM and Storm Cloud. This effort was

² Prior to PRISM, CSER and partners developed what became known as “RESTORE Field Plots.” These plots were funded by the RESTORE Act to facilitate a pivot to more accurate remote mapping solutions to help characterize forested landscapes at large and small scales within the Apalachicola Region. Essentially, RESTORE Plots facilitate both image- and lidar-based remote sensing analyses. A total of 248 RESTORE field plots were established between December 2017 and March 2018 prior to Hurricane Michael and covered 27 unique natural communities. Plots were strategically placed on public lands to help capture spectral values from remote sensing datasets, including Landsat, Sentinel-2, and NAIP imagery. Agricultural and urban landcovers were excluded to focus primarily on sampling the range of forest conditions in the Apalachicola Region. These plots proved critical for evaluating post-Hurricane Michael timber stand damage. These unique plots, designed by Dr. John Hogland of the USFS Rocky Mountain Research Station and are described in his Ph.D. dissertation (Hogland, 2019).

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

critical to the outcomes presented in this document and these plots are now available in perpetuity based on the overarching utility that field vegetation plots provide for validating remotely sensed spatial data. Simply put, had this not been in place prior to PRISM, it would have been difficult to conduct this project without significant and costly delays, or at all.

- The USFS Forest Inventory & Analysis Program funded the 2021- current Storm Cloud effort which was led by UF SPEC (Broadbent, et al.) and supported by CSER. This initiative provides a functional methodology and application platform beta for future USFS natural disaster response efforts. Moreover, the initial investment in CSER provided an operating template for PRISM and helped initiate the opportunity for Storm Cloud that have both proven to be a viable solution for hurricane, timber, and natural resource damage assessments.
- In 2017, in preparation for the RESTORE-funded Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project (Medley et al., 2023), National Forests in Florida staff helped procure 2018 ALS point cloud data over the entire Apalachicola Region. This effort was facilitated by our partners at the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) and Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWWMD), and funded directly by the NFWWMD, USGS, and USFS Region 8. This timely data acquisition proved invaluable for assessing post-Hurricane Michael storm damage by providing a strategic pre-Hurricane Michael timestamp that was supported by pre-existing ecological condition model (ECM) plots, other vegetation plots, and later accompanied by novel field vegetation plots used for highly accurate pre-/post-storm comparisons. This effort further enabled the original CSER Hurricane Michael analysis studies by St. Peter et al., 2020 and subsequent disaster assessment initiatives over the Apalachicola Region, including Storm Cloud.
- Both the 2018 ALS data and the 2020 ALS data acquired by the State of Florida were processed by the PRISM Team to assist with timely accurate multi-temporal analyses. Through a precision co-alignment process using highly accurate PRISM DLS data, the 2018 and 2020 ALS datasets currently exhibit an average locational difference of essentially zero centimeters among these datasets in some areas. This is discussed later in this document, but for all intents and purposes this has been a game-changer in terms of the analytical accuracy for multi-temporal analyses. This should be a standard operating procedure for all relevant future data collections.
- In our prior comparative, analyses, CSER drew heavily from data developed via our Relative Density Canopy Cover (RDCC) lidar workflow (St. Peter, et al., 2021) and used it to translate 11TB of raw lidar point cloud data (~22,000 LAS files) with over 375 billion lidar points into layers of meaningful information related to forest structure. The products were multi-band raster datasets (GeoTIFFs), where each band is described in Table 1. These raster datasets were created at a 5-m spatial resolution over the entire 22,900 km² (5,658,713 acres) Apalachicola Region. The data and derivatives also provided an invaluable pre-hurricane reference point for analyzing change across the regional landscape.
- The PRISM Project Team developed unique field-going support vehicles as mobile launch laboratories and other useful field support equipment including the “Off-Road Command & Control Station (ORC-CS).” This effort helped ensure PRISM’s operational efficiency even while traversing challenging terrain under difficult circumstances and inclement weather. This is described in greater detail in the Operational Support section of this document.
- PRISM also gained leverage via parallel RESTORE funding, numerous meticulously crafted novel field vegetation plots, and research momentum including critical scientific peer reviewed publications and student/post-doctoral associate funding, training and mentoring.
- The PRISM Project Team coordinated regularly through in person and virtual meetings, provided detailed Quarterly Progress Reports, and participated in a 2-day onsite regional project review in October 2023 coordinated with R8 Resource Information Management (RIM), Grants and

**Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study**

Agreements, and National Forests in Florida leadership. The Team also conducted regular outreach with local populations, including hikers, hunters, and visitors, in the field.

Figure 9. PRISM flight missions conducted using the Harris Aerial H6 EFI drone platform demonstrated remarkable endurance by flying over 14,000 km—equivalent to a flight from Tallahassee to the South Pole or over 40% of Earth’s equatorial circumference.

Table 1. List of the relative density canopy cover (RDCC) function output bands, variable name, and description of output variables. Variables are forest metrics derived from LAS point cloud input files.

Band	Variable	Description
1	Num_Returns	Total number of returns in cell
2	Num_GrndRet	Number of ground returns in cell
3	Num_1stRet	Number of first returns in cell
4	Grnd_Elev	Ground Elevations
5	Mn_RH	Mean of all Relative Heights
6	SD_RH	Std. Dev of all Relative heights
7	RHt_95th	Relative Height 95%
8	RHt_90th	Relative Height 90%
9	RHt_75th	Relative Height 75%
10	RHt_50th	Relative Height 50%
11	RHt_25th	Relative Height 25%
12	RHt_10th	Relative Height 10%
13	RHt_05th	Relative Height 5%
14	RD_2to10ft	Relative Density .6096-m to 3.048-m (Shrubs)
15	RD_10to20ft	Relative Density 3.048-m to 6.096-m (Low midstory)
16	RD_20to49ft	Relative Density 6.096-m to 14.935-m (High midstory)
17	RD_gt2ft	Relative Density all returns \geq .6096-m
18	RD_gt10ft	Relative Density all returns \geq 3.048-m
19	RD_gt20ft	Relative Density all returns \geq 6.096-m
20	RD_gt49ft	Relative Density all returns \geq 14.935-m
21	CC_gt2ft	Canopy Cover \geq .6096-m (based only on first returns)
22	CC_gt10ft	Canopy Cover \geq 3.048-m (based only on first returns)
23	CC_gt20ft	Canopy Cover \geq 6.096-m (based only on first returns)
24	CC_gt49ft	Canopy Cover \geq 14.935-m (based only on first returns)
25	MnRHgt2ft	Mean of all relative heights \geq .6096-m
26	MnRHgt10ft	Mean of all relative heights \geq 3.048-m
27	MnRHgt20ft	Mean of all relative heights \geq 6.096-m
28	MnRHgt49ft	Mean of all relative heights \geq 14.935-m

Subsequent PRISM Developments

As a follow-on to the CSER’s Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project completed in 2023 (Medley et al., 2023), CSER at FAMU is leading an unprecedented monitoring program and other restoration elements for the recently funded Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI) Strategies 2 & 3 Project. The ARRI Monitoring component, funded for a total of \$1,599,306 over four years, began on October 1, 2024, and now, via CSER includes collaborators from UF, FAMU, Florida State University (FSU), multiple organizations representing the State of Florida including Florida Department of Environmental Protection (FDEP), Florida Park Service (FPS), Florida Forest Service (FFS), and Florida Fish & Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC), as well as several private entities, and interested stakeholders.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

Of note, and highly applicable from a PRISM or agency management perspective, ARRI data recently collected over the newly acquired 17,000+/- acre St. Teresa Tract, divided between the Florida Forest Service and Florida Park Service, is proving very useful for refining project monitoring objectives. For all intents and purposes, and thanks to the excellent and timely land preparation work by our FDEP, FPS, and FFS partners, there are now multiple locations containing large acreages in the St. Teresa Tract near Alligator Point, Florida that can currently qualify as a “blank restoration canvas.” These key sites are also situated in a strategic and sensitive area for longleaf pine (*Pinus palustris*) habitat and contain or are adjacent to numerous freshwater and marine resources including wild eastern oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*) shoals and active oyster cage farming operations.

As a future deliverable to RESTORE for the ARRI Project, CSER has already applied advanced technology and methodologies partially developed during the PRISM Project to local and regional conservation and restoration lands within the Apalachicola Region in the Panhandle of Florida that may reveal new operating paradigms for ongoing multi-party landscape characterization and restoration initiatives. Over ARRI’s project time horizon, using advanced PRISM-like equipment, priority data collection initiatives will continue over federal, state, and private lands within the study area both preceding and following planned land management activities. Priority data collection sites include, but are not limited to, Bald Point State Park near Alligator Point, Apalachicola National Forest, Tate’s Hell State Forest, Telogia Creek Wildlife Management Area, and other locations of interest (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Map of priority restoration lands for the RESTORE-funded Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI) Project that began October 1, 2024, and runs through 2028.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

Throughout the ARRI Project, data products and derivatives collected from restoration priority areas, many of which were identified in Tate's Hell Strategy 1, will be processed and analyzed by the ARRI Monitoring Team (Jason Drake, Angelica Almeyda Zambrano, Eben Broadbent, and Paul Medley). Other CSER partners such as Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI), FAMU, and FSU will also participate in the monitoring effort and add significant value to ARRI's overall monitoring capabilities. This information will ultimately be used to inform ARRI ecosystem and hydrologic restoration strategies by providing benchmark structural condition data at scale for large areas of forested public lands. So far, through this monitoring and adaptive management (MAM) process, the advanced data collected over Bald Point State Park has already helped facilitate restoration decisions by regional, state and national programs. Moreover, this data will eventually help produce multi-dimensional product derivatives over large areas, in turn, to be used for advanced applications in geospatial ecology, fuels reduction, wildfire prevention, disaster assessment, etc. Relevant data and a selected set of derivatives will in due course be shared with partners and stakeholders to assist with future land management initiatives and as part of the comprehensive project deliverables to the RESTORE Council.

At this juncture, because of the advanced, highly dense ARRI lidar data that has just been collected, processed and analyzed by the PRISM/ARRI Monitoring Team, we felt compelled to include a preview in this report before the beginning of the PRISM data discussion to provide an accurate, up front representation of what can be considered a readily achievable post-PRISM state-of-the-art dataset (Figures 11 and 12). In addition to the information these extremely rich and dense drone-borne lidar point cloud datasets provide; they also offer a structural foundation for a series of tightly co-aligned preexisting ALS datasets and future fusion products (lidar + hyperspectral + thermal) that have the potential to reveal completely new methods of understanding and could hypothetically serve as robust large landscape AI training datasets. This data has already enabled the ARRI Monitoring Team to characterize forest stands in fine detail (even at the individual tree level) over key ARRI restoration focal areas to quickly make informed decisions about the next best steps following the land preparation activities by our state partners. However, long-term speculation on this issue is beyond the scope of this project and document, but it enables us to envision scenarios that could quickly lead to significant and lasting changes to the landscape manager's toolbox likely well before most federal or state management agencies are ready to embrace such impending colossal operational shifts. In our opinion, this cannot be overstated and should serve as a cautionary tale for looming technological disruptions in the near-to-mid-term.

Specifically, baseline datasets collected during early pre-treatment monitoring trials on the St. Teresa Tract of Tate's Hell State Forest and Bald Point State Park have already produced datasets that far surpass PRISM's lidar data aggregate nominal pulse densities (ANPD). For comparison, USGS QL0 (highest quality level) and QL1 airborne lidar nominal pulse density is 8 pls/m², while QL2 lidar is only 2 pls/m² (Table 2). There is also a QL3 lidar product from USGS 3DEP that has 0.5 pulse/ m² and a non-vegetated vertical accuracy of almost 40cm which, in our opinion, renders this nearly ineffective compared to drone lidar scans (DLS). The exceptionally dense ARRI DLS point clouds currently weigh in at a whopping ~2,200 pls/m² aggregate nominal pulse density (ANPD) accounting for an incredible ~1367% increase beyond PRISM data that was previously collected over the ANF which is significant, particularly when applied to large landscape modeling and analysis or even fine-scale digital mensuration at the individual tree level.

**Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study**

As compared to the aggregate nominal point density (ANPD) of PRISM data collected over the Apalachicola National Forest (~150 pls/m²), the most recent data collected over Bald Point State Park exceeds ANF PRISM dataset specifications by an order of magnitude. The point cloud for the northernmost treatment area (~87 ac.) shown in Figure 11 has an ANPD of 1,816 ± 811 pls/m² with a maximum pulse density of 9,908 pls/m². The ANPD for the southernmost treatment area (~119 ac.) is 1,943 ± 886 pls/m² with a maximum of 9,230 pls/m². Figure 12 presents a comprehensive analysis of young, mature, and uneven-aged sand pine (*Pinus clausa*) stands. These timber stands were used to derive tree height distributions from drone-borne lidar data collected on June 29, 2024, over Bald Point State Park (St. Teresa Tract). The ultra-dense lidar point clouds were segmented using Individual Tree Detection (ITD) methods with processing techniques developed by the ARRI Monitoring Team, providing precise and reliable tree heights along with other relevant structural metrics. The list of derivable metrics from these high-quality datasets is staggering and extremely revelatory. The level of detail that can be extracted from this information is unprecedented, and positionally speaking puts us at the on ramp of exponential adoption of this technology. There has never been a better time for the agency to fully engage.

Table 2. Lidar quality level requirements defined in the 3DEP Lidar Base Specification as determined by nominal pulse spacing/density and vertical positional accuracy requirements.

QUALITY LEVEL	DATA SOURCE	VERTICAL ACCURACY RMSEz (cm)	NOMINAL PULSE SPACING (NPS) meters	NOMINAL PULSE DENSITY (NPD) points per square meter	DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL (DEM) cell size (meters)
QL0	Lidar	5 cm	<= 0.35 m	>= 8 pts/square meter	0.5 m
QL1	Lidar	10 cm	<= 0.35 m	>= 8 pts/square meter	0.5 m
QL2	Lidar	10 cm	<= 0.71 m	>= 2 pts/square meter	1 m

Source: U.S. Geological Survey Topographic Data Quality Levels - <https://www.usgs.gov/3d-elevation-program/topographic-data-quality-levels-qls>.

Figure 11. Extremely dense drone-borne lidar point cloud datasets collected over two ARRI Project timber stand treatment areas (~240 ac.) on Bald Point State Park (St. Teresa Tract), near Alligator Point, Florida. Red lines are drone flight lines around forest stands demarcated by yellow lines. Overlapping red polygons indicate drone flight lines with side and end overlap to increase ANPD.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

Figure 12. Characterization of young, mature and uneven age sand pine (*Pinus clausa*) stands to derive tree height distributions using drone-borne lidar data collected on 6/29/2024 over Bald Point State Park (St. Teresa Tract), near Alligator Point, Florida. Ultra-dense (~2,200 pls/m² ANPD) lidar point clouds segmented using Individual Tree Detection (ITD) and processing techniques developed by FAMU’s CSER and UF’s SPEC Lab reveal tight and reliable tree heights and other relevant structural metrics.

Drone Lidar Scanning (DLS) and Imagery Data Collection

GatorEye

The GatorEye Uninhabited Flying Laboratory and drone-borne spatial data collection and monitoring platform is an advanced hardware assemblage pioneered by Drs. Angelica Almeyda Zambrano and Eben Broadbent from the University of Florida’s Spatial Ecology & Conservation (SPEC) Lab. Their system has evolved from decades of meticulous research in geospatial systems integration as well as long-term industry-academic partnerships between SPEC, [Phoenix LiDAR Systems](#), [Harris Aerial](#), [Headwall Photonics](#), and [Skyfront](#) among others combined with custom algorithms and workflows that facilitate large area geospatial data collections while employing an array of advanced, tightly co-aligned and complementary lidar, hyperspectral, thermal, and visual sensors. This NDAA-compliant system has gained keen interest from many faculty, staff and student researchers at the University of Florida, Florida A&M University and globally. These facts, along with the very high skill level and knowledge base of SPEC Lab personnel made it an easy choice to partner with especially since their interests in geospatial ecology align so well with CSER’s mission. In essence, GatorEye technology has empowered numerous

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

USDA and partner projects by providing top-tier access to unique next-generation geospatial data acquisition and processing technology that has been applied to large scale land management across the Apalachicola Region. In essence, the SPEC Lab has been developing new remote sensing technology for years because these systems have committed participants with “skin in the game.” These systems have been specifically assembled, adapted to and customized for the USFS PRISM Project. Consequently, the academic-industry-government partnership has afforded PRISM the very latest U.S.-made remote sensing technology and custom applications available anywhere (Figure 13). GatorEye, led by Angelica Almeyda Zambrano and Eben Broadbent, supports researchers at UF, Florida A&M University, USFS, and NRCS as well as globally through their commitment to land management, scientific exploration, and spatial ecology.

PRISM data collection efforts over the ANF, have utilized both the [GatorEye XL](#) and [GatorEye XTR](#) (Figures 13 & 14) platforms over the time horizon of the project. The latest customized XTR iteration features upgraded componentry, flight and inertial management systems and includes a fuel-injected gas-electric hybrid engine to facilitate large-area (1000s km²) data collection. The GatorEye XTR flight platform and sensor suite, completed in March 2024, is designed with mobility and robustness in mind. It was retrofitted with the full XL sensor suite and products from a recent collaboration with Phoenix Aerial and Skyfront. The XTR platform integrates a Phoenix Scout 32-beam lidar, a 61 MP visual camera, and a Skyfront Perimeter 8+ hybrid-powered flight platform. Additionally, the XTR version features enhanced weatherproofing and can be checked as baggage on commercial airlines. The next version of GatorEye, anticipated in 2025, will incorporate a second 61 MP camera with a zoom lens to enable simultaneous boresighted millimeter-resolution imagery for subset portions of the study area that require the utmost detail and accuracy. Numerous publications, case studies, datasets, visuals, and detailed hardware descriptions for various platforms and studies are available at www.gatoreye.org.

Figure 13. Dr. Eben Broadbent of the UF SPEC Lab supports PRISM on the Apalachicola National Forest and other locations through skilled UAS piloting of GatorEye XL as well as expert integration of the latest UAS and geo-positioning hardware and imaging/sensor systems. Building and testing of the SPEC Lab's GatorEye XL system flight platform and sensor fusion and integration were completed just prior to collection of the first PRISM data grid.

Figure 14. GatorEye XL (background) and the new XL-EFI mobile flying laboratory and data collection platform (foreground) used during the PRISM Project. While XL is a gas/battery hybrid, the engine is carbureted, but the XL-EFI is a fuel injected hybrid powered system with flight times exceeding 1.5 hours while carrying a 6-kg payload. A customized version of the XL-EFI system was used for latter portions of the PRISM Project, and for the St. Teresa Tract data shown previously in Figures 11 and 12. More information about GatorEye can be found in “The GatorEye Unmanned Flying Laboratory: sensor fusion for 4D ecological analysis through custom hardware and algorithm integration.” (Broadbent, et al., 2024)

Data Collection

Lidar and imagery data collected over the Apalachicola Ranger District used a “Block & Grid” system (Figure 15) designed by the PRISM Team at the project’s beginning to help plan, guide and track data collection activities. The block & grid system is divided into 278 individual 1.5 x 3 km grids contained within 7 blocks, each covering up to a maximum of 58 cells per block. These were frequently flown in half-grids (North+South or West+East). The total study area was $\sim 1228.36 \text{ km}^2$ (303,534 acres) plus re-flights and supplementary data that equates to $\sim 350,000$ acres of national forest land coverage. Subsequently, multiple collection periods for selected study grids or blocks were conducted to enable multi-temporal analyses related to assessing disturbance, change, vegetation structural characteristics and growth dynamics as they relate to management considerations. Additionally, there were a few grids that required re-flights due to minor technological malfunction of the lidar sensor. Thankfully, this was minimal and is discussed more in the next section.

The initial PRISM data collection campaign for Block #1 took place from Wednesday November 10th to Saturday November 13th, 2021, and the remainder of Block #1 was completed during the second

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

week of December. After collecting Block 1 data, the team decided to prioritize and improve processing workflows using this data to develop early high-quality examples of advanced high-density point clouds. Also, they further refined production processes, resulting in significant efficiency improvements. Subsequently, the next data collection was planned for January and February of 2022. However, this effort was preempted by Florida legislation resulting in a 4-month collection delay due to the forced grounding of all drones flown by all Florida state governmental agencies including state universities. In accordance with [section 934.50 of Florida Statutes](#), from January 1, 2022, through April 20, 2022, PRISM's UF partners were unable to use their existing drone systems to collect data. Fortunately, subsequent legislation ([State Rule 60GG-2.0075, F.A.C.](#)) was in place by April 20, 2023, and according to Gerard Steele from the Florida Department of Management Services, UF was able to resume data collection for this award as planned. The second and final round of data collection for Block #1 took place from Monday, May 16th to Friday, May 20th. Afterwards, because of the initial delay, the Team had to accommodate their teaching and research schedules which permitted intermittent flights until dedicated time blocks were available to continue uninterrupted collections. The final data re-flights were collected between 12/28/24 to 12/30/24 and were initiated as replacement flights due to equipment upgrades and changes in data processing techniques.

During the grounding period, UF partners used their time for maintenance and calibration of UAS flight and positional systems, as well as improved data processing and planning methods. As a cautionary tale, while this was Florida-specific legislation, there may eventually be other state and/or federal regulations that could affect the operational capacity of PRISM or similar UAS initiatives. Certainly, this was not the only potential risk to PRISM, some of which were outlined in the original proposal. Fortunately, no noteworthy incidents occurred during the 3-year PRISM Project. PRISM drone flights resumed in May 2023. Since the inception of PRISM, we further revised flight plans to reduce per-flight mission times and avoided flying in periods we have identified as having higher wind speeds and likelihood of rain or other inclement weather conditions. Additionally, close coordination with the Florida Interagency Coordination Center (FICC), which is a key component of the US Forest Service's fire operations in Florida, proved highly successful. FICC is responsible for coordinating federal interagency fire management activities and planning across the state. FICC works closely with the Florida Forest Service and other agencies to manage and respond to wildland fires, ensuring efficient use of resources and effective communication. They also handle the dispatch of resources for fire suppression and other emergency management activities, both within Florida and for out-of-state incidents. This coordination helps to maintain safety and effectiveness in managing wildfires and other emergencies and was vital to the safety and success of PRISM field operations.

Data collection over each grid took approximately 90 to 140 minutes of flight time to complete, not including transportation to and from each location, but included equipment setup and teardown. Occasionally, rain, fog, excess wind, hurricanes, fires, aviation hazards and other unfavorable flight conditions precluded data collection efforts that resulted in some collection delays. These conflicts were somewhat challenging logistically and operationally, but they were typically not overly limiting. Usually, these events would cause minor delays that sometimes resulted in flight location changes or temporary postponements, but never anything major. The following were notable Impacts on deliverable timelines:

- The initial 4-month grounding in the prime data collection window allocated for a large portion of the collection effort caused a downstream effect and scheduling conflicts that forced the PRISM Team to push data collection back accordingly.
- There were occasionally very slow procurement times for vital purchase of items such as hard disk drives and related processing equipment.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

- Challenges with navigating multiple agencies/organizations to move funding quickly and effectively was a definite bottleneck, but not insurmountable. This should be a future priority area for improvement.
- By not funding PRISM's secondary supportive proposal for FAMU's CSER which was intended to provide extensive data and derivative processing, the final PRISM deliverables were scaled down due to budgetary and time constraints. The original intent of this supplementary PRISM effort was to supply over 200TB of data including dense hypercubic fusion examples but was curtailed accordingly. This knowingly impacted the ability to fully explore the applicability of PRISM data for decision support. However, several case studies and examples have been included throughout this document and in Appendix A to help illustrate the tremendous value that PRISM-type data can provide to greatly assist land managers, and to help set the stage for future endeavors whether operationally, technologically, or educationally.
- As mentioned, wildfires and prescribed fire often cause significant delays and flight repositioning and will be the same almost anywhere on national forest lands.
- Hurricanes (at least 4) were a definite factor contributing to delays. Future flight plans should reduce activity during peak hurricane season, particularly late June through early October.
- There were also a few U.S. military aviation operations that occurred in military operating airspace over the Apalachicola National Forest.
- There were several other small delays such as data deliverable coordination that caused cumulative delays.
- All told, the PRISM Team was able to deliver products and reports within the allotted project time horizon while achieving a global data collection record simultaneously.

**Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study**

Figure 15. PRISM block and grid data collection system used to guide and track collection activities across the entire Apalachicola Ranger District located on the western half of the Apalachicola Nation Forest southeast of Tallahassee. Data were collected using v.1 and subsequently v.2 system collection protocols outlined in this document.

The PRISM Difference

Besides the material presented thus far and in Appendix A, Figures 16 through 22 are high-quality representations of why and how PRISM-style data is far superior to ALS and other lidar products (e.g., TLS) and derivatives, particularly when applied to timber and natural resource disaster assessments. Without the concentration and consolidation of data points (laser pulses) combined with expertly co-aligned imagery collected from meticulously calibrated sensors, it would be nearly impossible to produce such superior products compared to most commercially available data sources that land managers presently rely upon (e.g., USGS 3DEP ALS). While this technique is not preternatural, it is highly effective and requires great skill although it may come at the cost of efficiency (for now), which ultimately affects affordability. Currently, we believe this difference more than compensates for the slower data collection times and will ultimately prove effective and much more efficient, especially

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

as projects begin to capture economies of scale. Regardless, PRISM-type algorithmic remote sensing techniques are highly impactful and very promising. However, they will eventually be enhanced with emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, advanced sensors (including quantum sensors), edge computing, 5G+, and quantum computing, blockchain and data security, autonomous systems, and swarm technology, among others.

Specifically, in lidar data collection terms, PRISM-style flightline “sidelap” and “overlap” are powerful mechanisms that can be maximized to increase data density and the analytical potential of lidar point clouds. Although these terms are often used interchangeably, they have explicit but slightly different meanings: overlap includes sidelap and forward overlap, while sidelap refers to lateral overlap. In the case of PRISM data, both elements were maximized to ensure that all edges of each lidar data collection swath were merged effectively, providing dense uninterrupted coverage over large land areas. This technique, while more time-consuming, virtually eliminates data gaps and ensures that the entire area of interest is covered multiple times from different angles, increasing data density, robustness, and overall analytical potential (Crespo-Peremarch, P., et al., 2016). Essentially, both sidelap and flightline overlap are crucial for achieving high-quality, accurate LiDAR datasets and elevate PRISM-type data collection activities above others that may only achieve a maximum pulse density of 8 pls/m². Figure 16 below portrays this phenomenon with a blue data collection flightline gradient, where the color ramp represents 1-3 overlap flightlines. Thus, the entire grid is ultimately covered by 2-3 flightlines, translatable into solid tree stem maps derived from stacked, multi-directional data. The following bullet points expand on how these elements impact the bottom line:

- **Increased Point Density:** The overlapping areas receive multiple passes of LiDAR pulses, which results in a higher number of data points per unit area. This increased point density enhances the detail and resolution of the captured data.
- **Improved Data Robustness:** With more data points in the overlapping regions, there is a greater redundancy of information. This redundancy helps in identifying and correcting errors, leading to more accurate and reliable data.
- **Enhanced Surface Coverage:** Overlapping flight lines ensure that there are no gaps in the data, providing continuous coverage of the surveyed area. This is particularly important in complex terrains where single passes might miss certain features. However, as mentioned previously and depicted in Figure 6, there is a unique and specific purpose to single-pass drone flights related to rapid damage assessments.
- **Better Feature Detection:** Increased point density and redundancy improves the ability to detect and characterize small or subtle features on the ground, which might be missed otherwise. This is critical for digital forest mensuration and the characterization of large, detailed landscapes.

Also, the maximization of data overlaps is an effective technique that has been documented and field tested within the 3,800+ hectare Ordway Swisher Biological Station near Melrose, Florida managed by the University of Florida where over 10,000 trees have been segmented, stem mapped, and field verified (Magee et al. 2022). From this data, the UF SPEC Lab derived as many as 75 individual metrics per tree. Overall, these advantages make overlap sidelap an invaluable technique for lidar data collection, contributing to higher quality and more reliably accurate datasets. This is further depicted in Figure 17 where the image exhibits a tremendous amount of detail that can be analyzed and extracted from the data source. This image shows incredible features of PRISM’s grid-level data including transportation arteries, dense pine plantations with visible soil bedding, hydrologic features including ephemeral wetlands, and various types of longleaf pine habitat that includes wet prairies, mesic and wet flatwoods, sandhills, and other longleaf pine habitats. See Figures 19-22 for more examples that contrast ALS with DLS, some of which display dramatic post-hurricane changes and growth over a span of 6 years.

Figure 16. PRISM lidar data from collection grid # 7-35 over the Apalachicola National Forest (Apalachicola Ranger District) showing a blue flightline gradient of 1-3 flightlines ensuring the entire grid is ultimately covered by 2-3 flightlines. This technique is highly effective for producing robust tree-level “stem” maps from multiple directions across very large landscapes.

Figure 17. Ultra-dense lidar point cloud collected over the Apalachicola National Forest revealing unique landscape features across this highly diverse forested landscape. Zoom in to the image to reveal fine details that remain visible and clear to the naked eye at 500% magnification.

Figure 18. Roughness derivative from a PRISM data grid produced from tightly co-aligned and condensed GatorEye flightlines. Surface roughness is one of the most impactful features affecting the shape of the returned LiDAR-pulse waveform and when combined with complementary feature geometry it can reveal unique analytical potential (see below).

Notably, the roughness layer extracted from LiDAR data has several important applications including:

- **Environmental Monitoring:** Environmental monitoring is a principal tenet of [National Forest Management Act \(NFMA\) of 1976](#). In general, lidar-derived surface roughness helps assess landscape roughness, which can also influence lidar pulse width which is important for various environmental studies. Specifically, surface roughness data can help identify areas prone to soil erosion, which, in turn, helps with early detection and mitigation of erosion features, mainly when combined with soil type data. Public and private lands across the U.S. constantly struggle with soil erosion and loss which can have a dramatic impact on water quality and flow. These types of lidar derivatives can be very useful to help deal with land management challenges.
- **Landscape and Urban Planning:** Roughness aids in the extraction of relevant features, such as vegetation, buildings and other elements that are useful for landscape planning.
- **Flood Inundation Modeling:** Roughness helps predict how water spreads during floods by providing detailed information about the ground surface and man-made structures that can redirect flow. On national forest lands, there are many anthropomorphic features that can dramatically influence surface flows and flooding including roads, fire lines, soil bedding and ditches.
- **Road Maintenance:** Roughness data helps detect road roughness, which is crucial for identifying maintenance needs and improving traveler safety and comfort. Road maintenance can be costly for many national forest lands and by deploying the proper geospatial tools effectively, it can help lower maintenance costs. As mentioned, surface roughness can indicate erosion areas which is a very common issue with national forest roads, most of which are unpaved.

All told, these applications highlight the versatility and importance of the roughness layer in different fields, but all of PRISM's applications are relevant to public and private land management. In fact, a very important paper published in 2010 in the highly regarded Photogrammetric Engineering & Remote Sensing (PE&RS) journal explains how and why surface roughness is one of the most effective

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

datasets influencing the shape of the returned LiDAR-pulse waveform and when combined with complementary feature geometry it can lead to impressive, automated extraction results (Lin and Mills, 2010). In this paper, the authors examined several factors, including slope angle, scan angle, amplitude, and footprint size, in addition to surface roughness. Among these, surface roughness was identified as the most significant factor influencing the return pulse width. This fact alone indicates that roughness derivatives could serve as a primary dataset for AI-driven automated feature identification and extraction while serving as a critical AI model training layer for large landscape analytics.

Finally, one of the most influential factors for accurate temporal change analysis is achieving a very high degree of spatial co-alignment (both vertical and horizontal) among imagery (RGB, hyperspectral, thermal), airborne, terrestrial, and drone-borne lidar datasets, even if those datasets have different specifications, point densities, scan angles, spatial resolutions, and purposes. The PRISM Team has discovered that this orchestral assemblage of geospatial data is crucial for assessing storm damage and for that matter conducting any timber or natural resource disaster assessment with confidence. This cannot be overemphasized. Without highly accurate, tightly co-aligned applicable datasets, errors introduced into the geospatial analytical methodologies can sometimes completely negate the results themselves. Often, this goes unnoticed by technical analysts and researchers alike but can ultimately lead to erroneous conclusions that affect critical decisions about the actual damage and change across the landscape. Figures 19 through 22 below illustrate the high degree of co-alignment applied to PRISM data, where the vertical alignment can and does often have a mean difference of approximately zero and a standard deviation of just a few centimeters. This fact highlights the skill required to derive precision data collections to achieve the full accuracy potential of lidar, imagery, and derivatives, particularly as it relates to data fusion processes which may eventually redefine large landscape characterizations altogether. Moreover, this is not an “add-on” procedure but must be wholly integrated into the technology and workflows performed by seasoned professionals who understand the value and implications of this process. Also, a deep-rooted understanding of the natural resources being sensed is paramount and is a principal reason why PRISM is superior. In fact, this is the core of modern spatial ecology and will be the foundation of many if not all large landscape AI/ML training initiatives of the future. Now, with the horizontal and vertical alignment precision of PRISM well into the sub-centimeter range, combined with the cumulative flightline to flightline accuracy, and high degree of spatial co-alignment, the feasibility of extremely accurate virtual forest measurements for stem diameter/tapering, small branches, and ultra-fine features confirms that landscape scale 3D disturbance mapping is well at hand.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure 19. Comparative point cloud profile of highly co-aligned airborne lidar scans (ALS) and drone lidar scans (DLS) showing several trees with nearby groundcover and shrubbery. Points in red correspond to ALS while points in green represent PRISM DLS data.

Figure 20. Comparative point cloud profile of highly co-aligned airborne lidar scans (ALS) and drone lidar scans (DLS) showing a large single tree with nearby groundcover and shrubbery. Points in red correspond to ALS while points in green represent PRISM DLS data.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure 21. Like figures 19 and 20, comparative ALS and DLS point clouds show relative tree growth and loss over approximately 6 years post-hurricane Michael and include visible changes in groundcover and shrubbery also affected by prescribed fire over this same time. Red points relate to ALS while green represents DLS data. The growth overlap area at the top of the graphic appears dark (green on red).

34

Figure 22. Like Figure 21, the ALS/DLS comparison portrays tree damage and loss. Red trees are missing while green trees remain, including damaged trees (broken and bent) as seen in the center and right of the graphic.

**Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study**

Operationally speaking, PRISM has been a significant challenge primarily due to the size of the data collection effort and the fact that this was accomplished with a hexacopter versus a fixed wing drone capable of longer flight times. Nonetheless, the size of this data collection operation is significant in and of itself. To portray this in relatable terms, currently PRISM is 10x (or greater) the largest drone-borne lidar collection effort globally (Eben Broadbent and commercial collaborators, personal communication, 2024) and is equivalent to nearly 1% of Florida’s land area. In fact, PRISM is larger than the total land area of the 10 smallest countries around the world and almost half the size of the U.S. state of Rhode Island (Table 3).

Table 3. Size of the PRISM data collection area of interest relative to the 10 smallest countries, globally.

Country	Square Miles	Acres	Hectares
Vatican City	0.2	128	52
Monaco	0.75	480	194
Nauru	8.1	5,184	2098
Tuvalu	10	6,400	2590
San Marino	23.6	15,104	6112
Liechtenstein	61	39,040	15799
Marshall Islands	70	44,800	18130
St Kitts and Nevis	101	64,640	26159
Maldives	115	73,600	29785
Malta	122	78,080	31598
Total	512	327,456	132,517

In general, PRISM was designed to document anticipated costs, operational logistics, and applicability of the drone-borne lidar data for rapid disaster response and recovery missions and damage mitigation planning. Originally, there was a second proposal that was intended to accompany the PRISM data collection proposal that involved processing all the data into a series of wall-to-wall products and derivatives. However, this portion was not submitted due to policy changes that affected the Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration at FAMU. Nonetheless, many value-added data deliverables were provided by CSER and our partners that helped complete the report and provided numerous examples of how this data has been used successfully to provide invaluable information to form the basis of sound decisions related to best practices for resolving or mitigating storm damage to national forest lands (see Appendix A). Operational costs for PRISM are detailed later in this document.

As a follow-on to the RESTORE-funded [Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project](#) completed in 2023 ([Medley et al., 2023](#)), CSER at FAMU is implementing a monitoring program and other restoration elements for the recently funded [Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative \(ARRI\) Strategies 2 & 3 Project](#). The ARRI Monitoring component, funded for a total of \$1,599,306 over four years, began on October 1, 2024, and includes collaborators from UF, FAMU, Florida State University (FSU), multiple organizations representing the State of Florida, several private entities, and interested stakeholders.

As a Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 (THS1) deliverable to RESTORE, the ARRI Monitoring Team has already applied advanced technology and methodologies partially developed during the PRISM Project to local and regional conservation and restoration issues within the Apalachicola Region in the Florida Panhandle that may reveal new operating paradigms for future multi-party restoration efforts. Over ARRI’s project time horizon (2025-2028), using advanced PRISM-like equipment, priority data collection initiatives will continue over federal, state, and private lands within the study area both prior to and following planned land management activities. Significant data collection sites include, but are not limited to, Bald Point

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

State Park near Alligator Point, Apalachicola National Forest, Tate's Hell State Forest, Telogia Creek Wildlife Management Area, and other locations of interest in the southeast (see prior Figure 10). Data products and derivatives collected from restoration priority areas, many of which were identified in Tate's Hell Strategy 1, will be processed and analyzed by the ARRI Monitoring Team, as well as FAMU, UF and FSU faculty and students at FAMU and used to monitor and inform ARRI ecosystem and hydrologic restoration strategies. So far, this has already helped facilitate restoration decisions by regional and national programs. Moreover, this data will be used to produce multi-dimensional product derivatives over large areas, in turn, to be used for advanced applications in geospatial ecology. Relevant data and a selected set of derivatives will also be shared with partners and stakeholders as part of the project deliverable to the RESTORE Council.

Operational Support

ORC-CS

A big challenge for large area drone-borne data collections is to operate efficiently in the field with the proper equipment. For large-area drone-borne data collections, success hinges not only on having a well-organized flight plan but also on positioning yourself near highly variable targets in remote areas, often under extreme operating conditions. PRISM's solution is a highly equipped mobile spatial laboratory developed by UF's Spatial Ecology & Conservation (SPEC) Lab called the "Off-Road Command & Control Station (ORC-CS)." Completed in 2023, the ORC features a heavy-duty 4x4 Ford F-250 with a highly customized bed and payload space, capable of hauling up to 16,000 lbs. off-road. For PRISM, it also includes a trailer-mounted 50-70 ft. manlift for large-area visual line-of-sight data collection (Figure 23). While operational, the ORC maintains continual satellite communications (Starlink) to support all GatorEye mission operations, even in adverse conditions and remote terrain. The system also includes an optional transportation trailer with a vibration-absorbing 'trampoline' bed mount and drone crane for efficient single-person flight operations of GatorEye systems. Developed exclusively for PRISM, it is also used extensively in our Big Plot Network partnership for long-term monitoring of hurricane damage across the Southeast, integrating calibration and validation data into our Storm Cloud system as described previously.

ORCA-CS

A crucial factor in the success of water-based drone-borne data collection is the UF SPEC Lab's Ocean-Research Command and Control Station (ORCA-CS). This system, active as of March 2025, features a 22-ft Skiff with a customized drone launch and landing platform designed for mid to shallow water drone-borne and bathymetric data collection. This system is used primarily for collecting data in coastal and riverine systems, mangroves, and other blue carbon environments. Additionally, the vessel's utility as a platform for sideways-mounted bathymetric sonar is being investigated. ORCA-CS will be used extensively in our Big Plot Network partnership for long-term monitoring of hurricane damage across the Southeast, Florida Gulf and Atlantic Coast black mangrove migration, and for integrating calibration and validation data into our Storm Cloud system. As well, there is significant interest in using ORCA-CS to expand the data collection AOI around the St. Teresa tract that includes Bald Point State Park and a portion of Tate's Hell State Forest. This area is surrounded on three sides by the Gulf of America, Ochlockonee Bay, and Alligator Harbor, a 14,184-acre protected Aquatic Preserve that's a nursery for many game fish species and a critical habitat for marine turtles. These areas are also known for superb fishing, recreation, oyster mariculture, vistas, and scenic beaches.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

Field Equipment

In addition to the ORC and ORCA mobile laboratories, PRISM field operations were nicely equipped with many items that enabled the PRISM crew to remain in the field and complete the mission without interruption. The following were an integral part of PRISM mobile field operations:

- Towable hydraulic boom lift for maintaining visual line of site with the drone.
- Field-capable enclosed utility trailer.
- Shock dampening drone trampoline for damage prevention to GatorEye during transport.
- Ruggedized weather and shock resistant computing equipment, monitors, storage devices, etc.
- Starlink Internet is used for in-field data processing and transfer.
- Well-equipped drone repair kits for most types of repairs.
- Inverter and solar generators with ample charging capabilities and battery backup devices.
- Fully equipped ORC-CS based drone maintenance tool assemblage.
- Emergency safety equipment, including fire extinguishers, medical kits, and portable power.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure 23. The highly capable Off-Road Command & Control Station (ORC-CS) was developed exclusively for PRISM to facilitate drone-borne data collection and numerous other data collection efforts since development in 2023.

Costs

The following cost estimates are based on acres flown and total project costs of PRISM:

- Total acreage flown= 350,000 acres (1,416 km²)
- Total project cost = \$1,398,985
- Per acre cost = \$3.99 per acre (\$987 / km²)
 - NOTE: This should be considered a high-end per acre cost estimate. This cost does not factor in additional products (e.g., coaligned ALS — critical for damage assessment), although this was provided to the U.S. Forest Service at no additional cost.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

As a cost comparison reference:

- QL1 lidar ~\$0.35/acre, however, this is assuming a data collection over thousands of square miles (e.g., eastern Florida Panhandle), and the lidar point density is 8 pulses/m², compared to PRISM nominal aggregate point density of 100s of pulses per meter, 3) commercial lidar does not include visual imagery, nor RGB data encoded into LAS files, 4) commercial lidar also does not include lidar derivatives for timber applications such as canopy height models (CHMs)
- Commercial drone data collection to provide only *.las files is about \$6,500 to \$12,000 per day³.
 - These estimates assume relatively easy access to project sites for construction, architecture/engineering, etc. in urban and suburban locations. Therefore, \$12,000 per day is a very conservative cost estimate for a remote drone data collection effort such as the Apalachicola NF.
 - Assuming commercial vendors can collect ~500-1,000 acres/day⁴, it would cost at least \$4.2M to \$8.4M to cover the 350+k acres covered by PRISM⁵. This is at least 3 to 6 times more expensive and would not include tightly co-aligned ALS which are crucial for pre- and post-hurricane change detection. It would also not include raster derivatives (CHM), visual imagery, RGB data encoded on LAS files, and other deliverables which are included in the PRISM project.

Partners

Meaningful partnerships are vital to CSER. They are the backbone of our productivity and include federal, state and local agencies, industry partners including multiple academic institutions (FAMU, UF, FSU, FNAI, etc.). Specifically, the CSER partnership applied to the PRISM project has dramatically expanded our competencies for:

- Data collection & management including field vegetation measurements and reference conditions including transportation and built infrastructure assessments (e.g., culverts, low water crossings, ditch networks, flow impediments (roads as dams, flow restrictions from hydrologic design malfunctions)).
- Data processing & analytics including incorporation of AI/ML applied to landscape model simulations.
- Ecological change detection & monitoring.
- Biotic & abiotic elements, ecosystem processes, services, interactions, disruptions and linkages centered around vegetation, wildlife habitat, terrain, and water.
- Hydrologic modeling and water yield (local and landscape scale).
- Natural disaster vulnerability and risk assessments.
 - Extreme weather events, fire, disease, including:
 - Pre- & post-event change detection.
 - Forest health monitoring.
 - Fire and fuels risk assessments and monitoring.
 - Non-native/invasive species infestations and monitoring.
- Anthropogenic disturbance mitigation and restoration strategies.
- Erosion, landcover, sprawl, built infrastructure, transportation network consolidation, water channel modifications and diversions, terrain anomalies, archeological.

³ [FlyGuys, Inc. Drone Services](#) - Understanding potential costs.

⁴ [FlyGuys, Inc. Drone Services](#) – LIDAR Services.

⁵ [ROCK Robotic](#) – How to price drone lidar.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

- Socioeconomic modeling in the context of the above.

By assembling top-tier, highly relevant cross-disciplinary partnerships appropriate to our specific restoration and geospatial mission, we have been able to capture relevant data and metrics that will pave the way for similar initiatives moving forward. The following is a list of partners and participants the PRISM Team regularly interacts with:

- [United States Department of Agriculture](#)
- [U.S. Forest Service](#)
- [Natural Resources Conservation Service](#)
- [RESTORE the Gulf](#)
- [Florida A&M University](#)
- [The University of Florida](#)
- [Florida State University](#)
- [Phoenix LiDAR Systems](#)
- [Harris Aerial](#)
- [Headwall Photonics](#)
- [Skyfront](#)
- [Topflight Computers](#)
- Many other colleagues, collaborators and stakeholders.

Summary and Conclusions

Legislative Subjunction

40

Legislatively speaking, beyond timber and natural disaster assessments, PRISM is significant because it heightens agency management capabilities for national forests and related natural resources and important ecosystem services. Specifically, it has the potential to improve the agency's ability to comply with the [National Forest Management Act \(NFMA\) of 1976](#). NFMA is key federal legislation that governs the administration of U.S. national forests. Enacted as an amendment to the Forest and Rangeland Renewable Resources Planning Act of 1974, the NFMA was designed to address various issues concerning forest management, including the legality of clear-cutting practices. Some of the main objectives and provisions of the NFMA include:

1. **Forest Planning:** The NFMA requires the USFS to develop comprehensive plans for managing national forests. Forest plans must consider multiple uses and sustained yield principles, ensuring that forests are managed for a variety of purposes, including recreation, timber, watershed protection, and wildlife habitat.
2. **Public Involvement:** The act emphasizes the importance of public participation in the planning process. This ensures that the interests and concerns of various stakeholders, including local communities and environmental groups, are considered in forest management decisions.
3. **Environmental Protection:** The NFMA sets standards for timber sales and harvesting practices to minimize environmental impacts. This includes guidelines for reforestation, soil and water protection, and maintaining biodiversity.
4. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** The act requires the USFS to regularly monitor and evaluate the condition of national forests and the effectiveness of management practices. This helps ensure that forest management goals are being met and allows for suitable adjustments as needed (adaptive management).

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

Overall, the NFMA aims to balance the diverse needs and uses of U.S. national forests while protecting their ecological health and resource sustainability. The NFMA remains a significant piece of federal legislation aimed at ensuring the sustainable management of national forests. Specifically, it requires the USFS to develop comprehensive plans for the management of renewable resources, emphasizing multiple-use and sustained yield principles. Fast forward to August 22, 2002, when President Bush launched the [Healthy Forests Initiative](#) instructing the Departments of Agriculture and the Interior, along with the Council on Environmental Quality, to enhance regulatory processes to ensure quicker decisions, increased efficiency, and more effective outcomes in mitigating the risk of devastating wildland fires. Shortly thereafter, the [Healthy Forests Restoration Act \(HFRA\)](#) of 2003 was introduced in response to severe wildfires and a variety of forest health crises that resulted in federal legislation to help reduce the risk of destructive wildfires and improve the general health of forests through expedited processes for hazardous fuel reduction and forest restoration projects. The distinct connection between NFMA and HFRA lies in their shared goals of sustainable forest management and ecological health. Unambiguously, the NFMA laid the groundwork by establishing a framework for managing forest resources sustainably, which highlighted the need for ongoing forest health and risk management that was further codified in HFRA by addressing specific threats like wildfires and insect infestations and removing barriers to implement necessary forest management practices more efficiently. In essence, the NFMA's emphasis on sustainable management and ecological health set the stage for the HFRA's targeted actions to maintain and restore forest health in the face of new challenges.

In 2012, the U.S. Department of Agriculture introduced a new rule for "National Forest System Land Management Planning" ([36 CFR Part 219 Subpart A](#)). This rule helps create, update, and revise management plans for all National Forest System (NFS) units, ensuring that the individual forest management plans protect and restore ecosystems while supporting various uses and services. The "planning rule" aims to ensure the sustainability of ecosystems and resources, addressing the need for forest restoration, conservation, watershed protection, and species diversity. Additionally, it helps the U.S. Forest Service provide a steady flow of benefits, services, and uses of NFS lands, which create jobs and support the economic and social well-being of communities. The PRISM Project introduces new, powerful, and cost-effective tools to enhance the capabilities of federal land management agencies to sustainably manage national forests and grasslands which includes responding rapidly and effectively to disasters and threats, while upholding the legislative responsibilities to care for, maintain and improve public lands.

41

Other Agency PRISM-Type Use Cases

To date, UF SPEC and FAMU CSER through PRISM have collaboratively helped define the best practices for 1) conducting safe and efficient drone operations, 2) codification of proven, innovative, and repeatable workflows, and 3) leveraging emerging technologies such as machine learning and deep learning AI to produce some of the finest point cloud data and imagery available. Additionally, multiple parties, beyond the U.S. Forest Service have benefited from PRISM-type drone-based, ultra-resolution geospatial initiatives and repeatable data production methodologies including the USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS), U.S. Department of Interior (DOI) – U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service, Florida Department of Environmental Protection, Florida Park Service, Florida Forest Service, Florida Fish & Wildlife Conservation Commission, Florida Natural Areas Inventory - a Florida State University entity, and others.

For example, Figure 24 through Figure 26 below portrays a practical use case related to soil loss mitigation strategies implemented by the NRCS through RESTORE and the Gulf Coast Conservation

**Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study**

Reserve Program (GCCRP⁶) where conservation planning strategies are ongoing at two significant drainage paths on private agricultural and forested lands in rural Santa Rosa County, Florida, near Allentown, approximately 14 miles north of Milton, Florida. Over time, surface water runoff from upland agricultural fields has concentrated flow into two major gullies (Brock and Pugh), resulting in head cutting and lateral widening of drainage channels. This process has created soil erosion hotspots that empty directly into the West Fork of Big Coldwater Creek. The West Fork of Big Coldwater Creek merges with the East Fork forming Big Coldwater Creek, approximately 3.3 miles below Brock Gully at a bearing of 113°52'06". Eventually, the creek connects to the Blackwater River further downstream, which flows out through Blackwater Bay, East Bay, Pensacola Bay, and into the Gulf of America. Big Coldwater Creek is a popular recreational destination known for its tranquil, clear, cool spring-fed flowing waters, abundant wildlife, and diverse fishing, camping, and boating activities. The creek bottom primarily consists of river rock and sand with numerous sandbars. The shallow water limits motorboat activity until the confluence of the Blackwater River, making it an ideal destination for canoeing, kayaking and fishing. In fact, Big Coldwater Creek is a well-known Florida Panhandle “paddle trail” enjoyed by visitors year-round.

This first phase of the GCCRP project (Brock Gully) was funded with a total budget of \$1.5 million, and the initial construction effort is now complete. CSER/SPEC’s involvement in the Brock and Pugh Gully Projects entailed a straightforward data collection and processing effort to highlight the utility of this data and further inform NRCS conservationists. Specifically, the mission sought to accurately characterize the gully erosion sites and adjacent landforms to provide actionable information to agency administrators and land managers to help them make more informed decisions without waiting for a long period of time to acquire lesser data and derivatives which through traditional channels could have taken years. Essentially, all SPEC drone data collection took place in one day (including travel). The following day, point cloud data was processed and made available to the CSER Team for further analysis and report writing. This is a stark contrast to the typical agency operating protocols but shows both the utility and adaptability that this technology brings to the table. The second stage (Pugh Gully) is now in the pre-construction phase and benefited significantly from the information that SPEC/CSER provided in record time. Ultimately, this initiative will immediately and positively impact water flows into the West Fork of Coldwater Creek, and the Gulf of America. The benefits to all stakeholders were rapid, repeatable, and tangible.

⁶ For context, the GCCRP was originally established by the U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA) in Texas, Mississippi, Alabama, and Florida to protect and restore critical wildlife habitat and improve water quality through conservation activities, forest management plans, and wildlife habitat development. These plans and activities help identify and address natural resource concerns on private property throughout the Gulf Coast Region, particularly as they impact water resources.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure 24. General vicinity of the Brock and Pugh gully restoration sites located in the Western Panhandle of Florida north/northeast of Pensacola approximately 14 miles north of Milton, near Allentown, Florida.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure 25. Planar view of Brock and Pugh erosion gully sites in rural Santa Rosa County, Florida illustrating upland agricultural activities, the proximity, topography, and sinuosity of the adjacent West Fork of Coldwater Creek watershed located near Allentown, Florida. Point cloud data for this site was collected on April 28, 2023.

Figure 26. Post-construction high-resolution imagery and mid-construction 3D RGB colorized lidar point cloud data (inset) collected over a NRCS RESTORE GCCRP-funded gully (Brock) erosion project situated alongside the West Fork of Big Coldwater Creek in Santa Rosa County, FL near Allentown.

What's Next?

Regarding short- to intermediate-term growth for PRISM-type activities within governmental land management agencies, the integration of AI with next-generation PRISM-style data and advanced collection and processing technologies will likely happen faster than expected. Indeed, this progression has evolved significantly over the 3-year time horizon of the PRISM Project and these timelines will only continue to compress. Very soon, and perhaps even in 2026, we will see the demise of the long-standing Moore's Law⁷ that hypothetically designates the rate of technological change. This phenomenon is being facilitated by increasing rapidity of technological advancements in remote sensing, drones, robotics, AI, quantum sensors, quantum computing, and high-speed global satellite networks. Consequently, it is easy to imagine hyperbolic growth in remotely sensed lidar and imagery data collection technology for the remainder of this decade, and beyond. In short, this is a time of unprecedented change and ignoring this fact will incur significant risk.

Ultimately, this evolutionary process will clear a path for unique mechanisms that redefine corporate best practices at a minimum and will likely result in a complete retooling of agency roles and workflows that revolve around deploying and managing this type of technology within the context of broad area land management. The traditional workflows and silvicultural methods that we now recognize will probably be subsumed by rapid technological advancements that challenge the orthodoxy of long-held agency standards and beliefs. This will compellingly (not by choice) pave the way for innovative practices in mega-scale land management likely accomplished via autonomous devices that are constantly connected to global networks while analyzing data by relevant AI agents that will feed into larger AI-driven support systems. These events will undoubtedly evolve quickly, and agencies will likely struggle with how and when to embrace them. In due course, as is typically the case, industry will lead

⁷ Moore's Law is not a scientific law but rather an empirical observation and prediction that describes the trend of the increasing number of transistors on integrated circuits, which has historically doubled approximately every two years. This observation has guided the semiconductor industry for decades, driving technological advancements and innovation.

**Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study**

the charge, but this will necessitate new government-academic-industry partnership paradigms that break down the slow pace of technological adoption that is typical of governmental agencies. Managing the ensuing impacts on human and capital resources will be one of the biggest challenges land management agencies confront yet we encourage agency leadership to face this head-on and plan their future around it.

Finally, time is of the essence, and the U.S. should strive to remain at the forefront of this technological revolution in land management. Agencies should explore every available way to launch new PRISM-style endeavors in the hopes of gaining technological and operational advantages simply because the alternative is too costly. Also, in the interim, the opportunity costs for deploying substandard equipment and methodologies are exceedingly high. Inferior equipment, improperly trained personnel, and adopting the one-size-fits-all⁸ approach to this technology will result in inferior data and workflows that cannot be used to adequately or accurately characterize large landscapes. Presently, the agency needs skilled data scientists and technologists who understand how to produce, manage, and apply this data within the context of public land management and artificial intelligence. The near-term endgame is high quality landscape data that will become the next high-value commodity for training AI systems. Eventually, we predict this activity will be taken over by globally connected autonomous data and information collection systems (robots) that feed data into larger AI-driven analytical frameworks that provide land managers of the future with the immediate results they need to make effective decisions for the betterment of the resources they manage and society. On top of this, society is approaching AI singularity, the hypothetical future point where AI intelligence surpasses that of humans when AI begins to improve itself autonomously which will undoubtedly lead to irreversible societal and technological changes. All told, dramatic change is imminent, but the rest remains unclear.

⁸ On occasion, internal agency procurement processes confound job appropriate technology from being delivered to apt users (office and field) who can apply this to their specific subject matter areas. However, it is these individuals who are most familiar with the timber and natural resources they manage which is spread across multiple USFS units including Fire, Silviculture, Timber, Lands, Recreation, Ecosystems, Hydrology, Engineering, Archeology, etc. From our perspective, detailed PRISM-like forest structure and function data provides vital decision-making information to many of these resource areas, especially, Fire.

Appendix A⁹

Figure A.1. Lidar point clouds showing aggregate nominal pulse density (ANPD) differences between ALS and DLS used in the RESTORE-funded Tate’s Hell Strategy 1, PRISM and the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative.

Figure A.2. Graphical illustration of raw (unclassified) and classified drone-borne laser scanning (DLS) point cloud used to produce first order derivatives

⁹Derivatives in this appendix were processed by the Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER) at Florida A&M University (FAMU) from raw point clouds provided by the Spatial Ecology & Conservation Lab (SPEC) at the University of Florida (UF), Gainesville.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure A.3. Digital Terrain Model (DTM) derived from the classified ground points in Figure A.2. This DTM is a three-dimensional derivative, whereas the DEM in the upper right corner of Figure A.4. is a two-dimensional raster derivative using the same ground points from the point cloud in Figure A.2.

Figure A.4. Air photo (upper left) and first order raster derivatives produced from classified DLS point cloud shown in Figure A.2. The Digital Elevation Model (DEM, upper right) is a two-dimensional raster produced from classified ground points. The Digital Surface Model (DSM, lower left) is produced from all lidar points. The Canopy Height Model (CHM) is the difference between the DSM and the DEM and for forested areas provides the height of vegetation relative to ground level. DEM, DSM, and CHM raster derivatives are deliverables for PRISM.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure A.5. Additional first order raster derivatives which can be produced from classified DLS point clouds using [peer-reviewed](#), [open-source CSER workflows](#).

Figure A.6. Left- Canopy height model (CHM) from 2018 Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS), Middle- CHM from 2023 Drone-borne Laser Scanning (DLS), Right- CHM Differences (2018 ALS – 2023 DLS). CHM difference products help to translate extremely large lidar point clouds collected before and after a hurricane into concise and actionable datasets related to forest damage, however this is only possible with precise co-alignment of lidar point clouds.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

```
1 #DLS_ALS_PointCloud_to_CHM.R- workflow to convert 2018 ALS and 202x DLS point clouds to Canopy Height Model (CHM) rasters
2 # and to create a CHM difference map to visualize changes
3
4 packages <- c("lidR", "sf", "raster", "terra", "tidyverse", "dplyr")
5 lapply(packages, require, character.only = TRUE)
6
7
8 #1) Convert DLS LAS files to CHMs using lidR. Note- using already normalized DLS LAS files
9
10 ## a) Create LASCatalog for DLS LAS files
11 ctg <- readLASCatalog("\\PathToDLS_LASFiles\\")
12 opt_output_files(ctg) <- "\\PathToDLS_CHM_OutputFiles\\dlschm_{ID}"
13 opt_chunk_size(ctg) <- 500 #Note- adjust as needed for efficient processing
14 opt_chunk_buffer(ctg) <- 20 #Note- adjust as needed for efficient processing
15
16 ## b) Create DLS CHM raster at 0.5 m resolution. For more info see: https://r-lidar.github.io/lidRbook/dsm.html
17 dls_chm <- rasterize_canopy(ctg, res = 0.5, algorithm = p2r()) #Note this creates an in memory vrt raster, files are written to folder above
18
19
20 #2) Convert 2018 ALS LAS files to CHMs
21
22 ## a) Create LASCatalog for ALS LAS files, drop withheld and noise points
23 ctg <- readLASCatalog("\\PathToDLS_LASFiles\\", filter = '-drop_withheld -drop_class 7 18')
24 opt_output_files(ctg) <- "\\PathToALS_NormalizedLAS_OutputFiles\\alsnlas_{ID}" #1st write normalized LAS files to temp dir
25 opt_chunk_size(ctg) <- 500 #Note- adjust as needed for efficient processing
26 opt_chunk_buffer(ctg) <- 20 #Note- adjust as needed for efficient processing
27
28 ## b) Normalize ALS LAS files (height above ground). For more info see: https://r-lidar.github.io/lidRbook/normalization.html
29 nctg_temp <- normalize_height(ctg, knnidw())
30
31 ## c) Create LASCatalog for ALS normalized LAS files, filter out erroneous "bird shots" and "underground" shots
32 nctg <- readLASCatalog("\\PathToALS_NormalizedLAS_OutputFiles\\", filter = "-drop_z_below 0 -drop_z_above 50")
33 opt_output_files(nctg) <- "\\PathToDLS_CHM_OutputFiles\\alschm_{ID}"
34
35 ## d) Create ALS (2018) CHM raster at 0.5 m resolution For more info see: https://r-lidar.github.io/lidRbook/dsm.html
36 als_chm <- rasterize_canopy(nctg, res = 0.5, algorithm = p2r())
37
38 #3) Calculate CHMdifference raster (2018 ALS minus 202x DLS)
39
40 ## a) Match extents through resample
41 alschm_rs <- resample(als_chm, dls_chm)
42
43 ## b) grid math
44 chmdiff <- dls_chm - alschm_rs
45
46 #4) Optionally- visualize the differences
47
48 ## a) Creating simple custom palette where...
49 ## trees present in 2018 but not in 202x are red (e.g., trees blown over or leaning heavily from original position)
50 ## trees not present in 2018 but are present in 202x are blue (e.g., new location of crowns that are leaning... OR tree crown lateral growth)
51 custom_palette <- colorRampPalette(c("blue", "white", "red"))(100)
52
53 ## b) Create simple plot
54 plot(chmdiff, col=custom_palette, main="Canopy Height Model Changes (202x-2018)")
55
56 #5) Optionally- write CHMdiff raster to disk
57 ##(note- DLS and ALS CHM rasters are already in folders listed above in lines 12 and 33 respectively)
58
59 writeRaster(chmdiff, "\\PathtoCHMdiff\\chmdiff.tif", gdal=c("COMPRESS=NONE", "TFW=YES"), datatype="FLT4S")
60
```

Figure A.7. R code workflow used to derive canopy height models (CHM) derivatives as well as the CHM difference raster from Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) and Drone-borne Laser Scanning (DLS) point clouds from PRISM. This workflow was used to produce the CHM differences shown in Figure A.6 and other subsequent figures.

**Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study**

Figure A.8. Some CHM differences are the result of leaning trees from heavy hurricane winds. For example, in the middle panel, the red pixels in the black rectangle correspond to where a large longleaf pine crown was in 2018 (ALS CHM) but is no longer present in 2023 (DLS CHM). In contrast, blue pixels show where the tree crown is in 2023 after strong wind gusts from Hurricane Michael. This can be seen clearly in the clipped point clouds in the right panel. Sparser points on the right represent returns from the pine tree crown in 2018 from ALS (note colors represent height aboveground where blue = lower returns and red= higher returns). On the left side of that same panel, the denser points are 2023 DLS lidar returns from the crown and bole of the same pine tree (colors are true RGB colors from DLS).

Figure A.9. Other CHM differences are the result of trees which are completely blown down by heavy hurricane winds.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure A.10. Demonstration area locations selected explore the utility of lidar CHM difference products shown in more detail in figures below. Early in the PRISM Project a proof-of-concept area was chosen to analyze CHM differences between 2018 ALS and 2020 ALS data. After PRISM DLS data was collected, three 50-acre demonstration areas were chosen across a damage gradient from low to moderate to high damage from Hurricane Michael. The raster data in the background is from a large-scale rapid hurricane damage assessment completed by CSER soon after Hurricane Michael where gray pixels represent no damage and brighter yellow areas represent greater losses of basal area (St. Peter et al. 2020).

Figure A.11. Proof of concept area for damage assessment showing 2018 ALS (Pre-Michael).

Figure A.12. Proof of concept area for damage assessment showing 2020 ALS (Post-Michael).

Figure A.13. Proof of concept area for post-hurricane damage assessment showing canopy height model (CHM) differences (2018 ALS minus 2020 ALS).

Figure A.14 Close-up of Figure A.13 Red = downed trees, blue = leaning trees.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure A.16. Additional field photo points were used to verify forest damage including this area where only a single tree was killed. Left = field photo from 2022, middle- ALS 2018-point cloud, right = DLS 2022-point cloud from PRISM.

Figure A.17. Field photo point from an area where a small group of trees was killed. Left = 2022 field photo, middle = ALS 2018-point cloud, right = DLS 2022-point cloud from PRISM.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure A.18. Field photo point from an area where a larger group of trees was killed. Left- field photo from 2022, middle = ALS 2018-point cloud, right = DLS 2022-point cloud from PRISM.

Figure A.19 For the same area shown in Fig A.18 it is important to note that drone lidar also collects true color (RGB) data for each lidar point returned. This information can be used to differentiate returns from bare ground/roads and even downed trees.

**Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study**

Figure A.20. 50-acre light hurricane damage assessment demonstration site (see Fig A.10). Left= Canopy Height Model (CHM) from ALS 2018, middle= CHM from DLS 2023 PRISM data, right = CHM differences (2018 ALS minus 2023 DLS). Overall, there were only minor differences resulting in a mean pixel level difference of -0.85 m (most likely due to tree growth offsetting losses of some trees).

Figure A.21. 50-acre moderate hurricane damage assessment demonstration site (see Fig A.10). Left= Canopy Height Model (CHM) from ALS 2018, middle= CHM from DLS 2023 PRISM data, right = CHM differences (2018 ALS minus 2023 DLS). Overall, there was a mean pixel level difference of 1.5 m, illustrating that there were more trees present in 2018 than in 2023.

Figure A.22. 50-acre heavy hurricane damage assessment demonstration site (see Fig A.10). Left= Canopy Height Model (CHM) from ALS 2018, middle= CHM from DLS 2023 PRISM data, right = CHM differences (2018 ALS minus 2023 DLS). Overall, there was a mean pixel level difference of 6.3 m, illustrating that there were substantially more trees present in 2018 than in 2023.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI) The PRISM Case Study

```

1 #PointCloud_to_ITD_Trees.R- workflow to detect individual trees from ALS or DLS point clouds
2
3 packages <- c("lidR", "sf", "raster", "terra", "tidyverse", "dplyr")
4 lapply(packages, require, character.only = TRUE)
5
6
7 #1) Read LAS file (from ALS or DLS) into memory
8
9 las <- readLAS("\\PathToDLS_LASFiles\\lasfilename.las")
10
11 #2) Normalize the las object so Z values are relative to ground level (Note- skip if already done)
12 ##For more info see: https://r-lidar.github.io/lidRbook/normalization.html
13
14 nlas <- normalize_height(ctg, knnidw())
15
16 #3) Detect individual trees using local maxima filter on point cloud data
17 ##For more information on Individual Tree Detection and Segmentation in lidR see: https://r-lidar.github.io/lidRbook/itd.html
18
19 itd_trees <- locate_trees(nlas, lmf(ws = 4))
20
21 #4) Optionally- Visualize point cloud with tree points
22 ##Note- this is recommended only for small areas (< 5 acres / 2 hectares).
23 ## Subsets of large LAS files can be created in lidR using filters when LAS file is read to memory or using the filter_poi function
24
25 x <- plot(nlas, bg = "white", size = 4)
26 add_treetops3d(x, itd_trees)
27
28 #5) Optionally- write ITD tree results to shapefile using simple features (sf) package in R
29 st_write(itd_trees, "\\PathToShape\\itdtreefile.shp", SHPT = POINT)
30 ##Note- the output shapefile will have the same XY coordinates as the LAS file used to create it.
31 ##The Z values represent the height (above ground) of each detected tree (Z is in same vertical units as LAS file)

```

Figure A.23 To provide greater insight into the magnitude of hurricane damage, CSER developed a workflow for individual tree detection (ITD) from ALS and DLS point clouds. This R-code workflow was applied to all three demonstration areas (Fig A.10) to estimate changes in tree size distributions from Hurricane Michael (see figures below).

Figure A.24. Graphical comparison of how ALS and DLS point cloud density can result in subtle differences in individual tree detection (ITD). It should also be noted that suppressed trees (i.e., understory trees directly underneath a canopy tree) are also not detected in the current ITD workflow.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure A.25. 50-acre light hurricane damage assessment demonstration site (see Fig A.10). Upper panels show 2018 ALS (upper left) and 2023 DLS (upper right) point clouds with ITD tree locations. The lower left panel provides a histogram of tree height distribution from ALS and DLS ITD results.

Figure A.26. ITD data was also used to segment tree crown areas from 2018 ALS (left) and 2023 DLS (right) point clouds for the 50-acre light hurricane damage assessment demonstration site.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure A.27. 50-acre moderate hurricane damage assessment demonstration site (see Fig A.10). Upper panels show 2018 ALS (upper left) and 2023 DLS (upper right) point clouds with ITD tree locations. The lower left panel provides a histogram of tree height distribution from ALS and DLS ITD results.

Figure A.28. ITD data was also used to segment tree crown areas from 2018 ALS (left) and 2023 DLS (right) point clouds for the 50-acre moderate hurricane damage assessment demonstration site

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure A.29. 50-acre heavy hurricane damage assessment demonstration site (see Fig A.10). Upper panels show 2018 ALS (upper left) and 2023 DLS (upper right) point clouds with ITD tree locations. The lower left panel provides a histogram of tree height distribution from ALS and DLS ITD results.

Figure A.30. ITD data was also used to segment tree crown areas from 2018 ALS (left) and 2023 DLS (right) point clouds for the 50-acre heavy hurricane damage assessment demonstration site.

**Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study**

Figure A.31. The CSER individual tree detection (ITD) workflow was also applied to 2023 PRISM DLS data to map the estimated tree size distribution of all trees (n= 10,385) in an Apalachicola NF stand where field data was collected in 2020. For this 74-acre young longleaf pine stand, 12 variable width Common Stand Exam (CSE) plots were used to sample a total of 65 trees. In the lower left panel, the relative distribution of tree heights from the field (gray histogram) and lidar (transparent blue) histogram reveals a great deal of overlap. ITD tree heights were also converted to DBH values using a published allometric relationship for longleaf pine (Gonzalez-Benecke et al. 2014), and the distribution of DBH from the ITD results were also compared to the field DBH distribution (lower right histograms). In this case, the DBH distributions matched very closely, however site indices can result in over or under estimation of DBH values and may need to be considered for the most accurate results.

Transforming Disaster Response and Forest Assessment using Remote Sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)
The PRISM Case Study

Figure A.32. Post-hurricane high resolution (0.5 m) wall-to-wall Canopy Height Model (CHM) for the Apalachicola Ranger District.

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